

Types of Stem Cells and Their Uses in Bioengineering and Medicine

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Abstract - Nowadays term “stem cells” is getting more public recognition than ever. The purpose of this article is to give a clear insight on basic information about stem cells. The analysis starts with history, which gives a background to knowledge we possess at the very moment. Presented characterization of each type of the cells, from both physiological and histological point of view, shows capabilities and limitations connected with their way of functioning. Distinction between cells present in young and adult organisms reveals their importance in different stages of life. Numerous places where stem cells can be found, especially in grown up organism, highlights their essential role in proper functioning. Ongoing stem cell research allowed us to induce the cells in laboratories, which opened up new possibilities for using stem cells in therapies and bioengineering. Even though it is only performed experimentally, stem cells may be used to create meat, without the need to breed the animals. Furthermore, soon we may find plant stem cells as an ingredient of skin cosmetics. However, there are still many unknowns when it comes to clinical applications – stem cell - based therapies are slowly becoming more and more possible to apply, giving hope for developing treatments for now untreatable or severe conditions. Yet, there are still many unknowns when it comes to such therapies.

I. INTRODUCTION

For centuries, scientists and researchers have been captivated by the physiology of living organisms. Along with the biggest discoveries there was curiosity that pushed us into understanding the rules of existence. Probably the most intriguing aspects of living organisms is their ability to regenerate. Although our understanding of this process has improved significantly in recent years, a vast amount of its mechanisms still remains unknown.

Stem cells (SCs) are undifferentiated cells that have not yet acquired the characteristics of any specific tissue but retain the ability to develop into specialized cell types. Physiologically, they are classified as either embryonic stem cells (ESCs) or adult stem cells (ASCs). SCs can be also induced (called induced pluripotent SCs) or pathological, usually present in cancers (cancer SCs). Due to their potency, they can be divided into: totipotent, pluripotent, multipotent and unipotent.

The term “stem cell” first appeared at the end of the 19th century. Initially, it functioned mainly as a theoretical concept used to describe tissues capable of self - renewal which made it possible for the long living organism to be comprised of cells with much shorter lifespan.

This terminology changed when Ernst Haeckel, a German biologist and Darwinist, created a concept for multicellular organisms to have their origin in primordial cells. His idea grew out of observations of embryonic development and the distinction between fertilized and unfertilized eggs. Thus, he used the term *stanzelle* (stem cell in German) in two contexts: a one celled organism that is an ancestor for multicellular organisms and a fertilized egg marking a beginning of a new life.

Definitely worth mentioning is a hypothesis about origins of tumours by Cohnheim. In 1877, he proposed that certain tumours arise from embryonic remnants, meaning cells that were not used during early development. According to his theory, once these dormant cells gain sufficient access to blood supply, they begin to proliferate. Cohnheim later extended this idea to explain physiological bursts of cell growth seen during pregnancy and puberty. Although he did not explicitly use the term “stem cells” in his work, the parallels between his hypothesis and later concepts of stem cell biology are unmistakable.

In a similar to Cohnheim’s way, haematologist Pappenheim also claimed tumours had their origin in stem cells. By examining the blood of amphibians he came to conclusion that red and white blood cells have the same precursor. Furthermore, he believed that the “mother cells,” as he often referred to them, were in some way comparable to embryonic cells, because they were able to differentiate into any blood cell or even other tissues.

One of the major milestones in the discovery and classification of stem cells occurred in the early 1960s. At that time, the existence of hematopoietic stem cells was demonstrated by two Canadian scientists, James Till and Ernest McCulloch. In 1961, during experiments on mouse bone marrow designed to study how cells respond to radiation, they observed cell colonies with the ability to self-renew. This finding led them to describe these cells as stem cells, and they even referred to the newly formed colonies as clones of the original cells. The design of the experiment and its results were published in 1963.

At the same time, similar experiments were carried out by Siminovitch. By using chromosomal markers induced by radiation, he was able to identify both the individual cell clones within colonies and the hematopoietic stem cells themselves. Mice were injected with marked bone marrow, and after two to six months had passed, the animals were examined. Out of 51 mice, 8 showed a high level of the marker in the thymus, 6 had lower levels, and in 15 the marker was present only in the bone marrow. Additionally, 6 mice had the marker in both the marrow and the thymus. The remaining animals showed no trace of it. These findings demonstrated that the cells forming the thymus could originate from the same clones as those observed in the colonies. The results of this experiment were published in 1967.

Another milestone appeared almost twenty years after the discovery made by James Till and Ernest McCulloch. In 1981, embryonic stem cells (ESCs) were successfully isolated for the first time by two biologists, Martin Evans and Matthew Kaufman. The cells were obtained from mouse blastocysts. After analysing them, it became clear that they had a normal mouse karyotype and retained the ability to differentiate. Although the initial experiment was successful and the technique became available, scientists needed another twelve years to fully achieve the development of mice derived from these isolated ESCs. This accomplishment ultimately confirmed the pluripotency of embryonic stem cells.

In 1998, human ESCs were successfully derived for the first time. The work was carried out and later described by Dr. James Thomson, an American scientist. The extracted cells maintained their ability to differentiate into all three germ layers or to form trophoblast for four to five months. In consequence such discovery gave a lot of hope to develop new therapies that might have

been hopeful for many people suffering from incurable conditions. However, because the method required the destruction of human embryos, the research quickly became the subject of ethical controversy. As a result, further studies were restricted, and the information released to the public was limited.

In 2006 Dr. Shinya Yamanaka, Japanese researcher, discovered a possibility to transform somatic mouse cells into cells resembling pluripotent stem cells. The result was achieved by forcing expression of genes specific for embryo cells and suppressed in somatic cells using a retrovirus to transduce selected genes. The resulting cells, named induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs), showed key features of pluripotent stem cells, including the ability to form tissues derived from all three germ layers. However, errors in DNA methylation were identified, which prevented these cells from giving rise to viable chimeras.

II. PHYSIOLOGICAL AND HISTOLOGICAL CHARACTERISATION

Stem cells are undifferentiated cells present at every stage of an organism's life. They are characterized by their ability to self-renew, proliferate, and differentiate into various cell types under appropriate conditions. These properties make them essential for organismal development as well as for the maintenance and regeneration of tissues. Stem cells can be classified in two complementary ways: according to their differentiation potential and according to their origin. Based on their potency, they are categorized as totipotent, pluripotent, multipotent, oligopotent, and unipotent. In terms of origin, stem cells are divided into embryonic (ESCs), fetal, and adult stem cells.

Totipotent stem cells are able to differentiate into all cells and tissues of the organism, both embryonic and extra-embryonic. These cells have the highest potential. The example of totipotent cell can be first stadiums of blastocyst up to 4-8 cells stadium and zygote which is formed after an egg is fertilised by a sperm. When these cells are subjected to leukemia inhibitory factor (LIF) they are dividing but without these factor they start to differentiate.

Next there are pluripotent stem cells (PSCs). They are able to form into all types of specialised adult cells of the organism originated from all three germ layers: ectoderm, endoderm and mesoderm but they can't create extra-embryonic structures such as placenta. PSCs can also form teratomas. In some cases the activity of telomerase can be lower in pluripotent cells. When something like that happens it can cause inability to self-renewal its population. To these types of cells belong embryonic stem cells derived from primitive node of blastocyst and induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs).

Multipotent stem cells have more limited ability to differentiate. They have potential to transform into specialised cells of the same lineage. That means that multipotent cells originate from the same germ layer. An example of these cells can be haematopoietic stem cells (HSC) which develop into blood cells enabling haematopoiesis and function of circulatory and immune systems or mesenchymal stem cells (MSC) which can differentiate into at least adipose tissue, cartilage and bone tissue. MSC are similar to fibroblasts in built and growth. After differentiation multipoint stem cells can transform into oligopotent stem cell. It causes restriction of its ability to differentiate its cells of only one lineage.

Oligopotent stem cells are able to transform into at least two lineages from within one tissue. Typical example of these cells can be hematopoietic stem cells which can transform into myeloid and lymphoid lineage.

Finally unipotent stem cells which have the most restricted capabilities to differentiate. They are also called progenitor cells. These cells are only able to transform into one type of specialised cells for example satellite cells transform into skeletal muscles, epidermal cells into keratinocytes or limbal cells into corneal epithelium.

In case of division by the origin firstly we have embryonic stem cells which come from the inner mass of preimplantation embryos. They are totipotent and pluripotent. From this cells can form fully developed organism. These cells can be identified by presence of specific transcription factors- Nanog and Oct4, which help maintaining the cell in undifferentiated state.

Then there are fetal stem cells. They are multipotent which means that they are able to proliferate intensively and can be divided into several types for example haemopoietic or mesenchymal cells. They can be isolated from bone marrow, fetal blood or fetal tissues. They have less immunogenic properties than adult stem cells originated from for example bone marrow.

Adult stem cells are either multipotent, oligopotent or unipotent, but mostly they are dominated by unipotent cells. Even if the unipotent cells have the lowest ability to differentiate they are necessary for a normal function of tissues and organs. These cells derive from an adult tissue. In the course of their life adult stem cells produce two types of cells: one identical copy and the other which is daughter cell with characteristic functions and morphology. Adult cells are typically dormant cells - they are metabolically inactive and are not dividing but when the tissue becomes damaged the cells activate and start to divide which causes to create new stem cells or remould already existing cells into specialised ones. This process is called regeneration of tissue or organ. Adult somatic stem cells can produce induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs), reprogramming them to the state of ESC. They are similar to ESC in terms of surface antigens, gene expression, telomerase activity and ability to proliferate. iPSCs can also differentiate into cells of three germ layers. Contrary to the ESC the iPSC are less ethically controversial because they can be sourced from almost all adult cells and are not limited, what in case of embryonic cells is problematic because the only source of them are embryos. Reprogramming of these cells is possible because of few genes: Oct3/4, Sox2, Klf4 and c-Myc

Some stem cells called tissue-resident stem cells can be located in a niche, place which can control ability to differentiate and self-renew. It protects stem cells by physical interaction and transmission of signals necessary for proper functioning. Niche places have a huge role in tissue repair by activating dormant cells by specific signals. Some studies suggest that origin of the cells connects to ontogenesis. All types of stem cells show expression of Bcrp1 gene. This gene is responsible for keeping the cells in undifferentiated stage. It is worth mentioning that not every organ in the body has a stem cell for example despite intensive research scientists couldn't find stem cells for cardiomyocytes in the heart or in pancreas there are no stem cells for insulin producing cells.

III. SOURCES OF THE STEM CELLS

We usually associate bone marrow or adipose tissue with the sources of stem cells. But the subject is more difficult. Different structures produce various kinds of stem cells depending on their source.

One of the first types of cells are the totipotent Embryonic stem cells (ESC). They are able to differentiate into any type of cells. Germ layers are formed from these cells. They are found in blastomeres of the dividing zygote. There are also pluripotent stem cells that occur in the inner cell mass of the blastocyst embryonic node. They can differentiate into any cell type of the adult organism. They are present in both humans and animals. In the 1980s, the mouse embryonic stem cell line was isolated for the first time from the inner cell mass. ESC can also be obtained from a 5-day-old in vitro of inner cell mass (ICM) or from a blastocyst obtained from embryonic germ cells. Using genetic manipulation, it is also possible to obtain induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSC) from somatic cells e.g. from fibroblasts or more and more frequently used mononuclear cells from blood. By stimulating genes that play a role in controlling embryonic development, cells with pluripotent properties can be obtained. This method involves introducing into the somatic cells four genes (Yamanaki cocktail (Oct4, Sox2, Klf4 and c-Myc)) which are active in embryonic stem cells. As a result, they are transformed to their original state, typical of embryonic stem cells. These sorts of cells are only produced in the laboratory.

In the tissues of an adult organism, we can identify another type of stem cells- adult stem cells (ASC)/ somatic stem cells (SSC). The source of these cells can be bone marrow, peripheral blood, nervous tissue, adipose tissue, cornea, retina, dental pulp, liver, skin, pancreas and intestinal tract. They demonstrate either multipotent or unipotent properties. The unipotent cells include:

- skeletal muscle satellite cells, which are small cells located under the basal membrane of the muscles

- limbal cells and eye stem cells that are located in the corneal epithelium and retina. They were found in the retina of the rat eye. They have been isolated from humans too. Corneal stem cells were located in the limbal niche.

- epidermal stem cells- They are found only in the basal (reproductive) layer.

- Spermatogonia stem cells (SSC) which are the only cells that self-renew and differentiate throughout the life of men. In mammals, primordial germ cells (PGC) are initially formed. Then, they travel to the seminal tubules where they become gonocytes. After birth, the gonocytes migrate towards the basement membrane of the sperm-forming tubule and differentiate into spermatogonial stem cells.

The somatic multipotent cells include:

- intestinal epithelial stem cells that have been found in intestinal crypts

- hair follicle stem cells

- hematopoietic stem cells (HSC)- These are cells isolated from peripheral blood or bone marrow. They can differentiate into specific types of blood cells. They migrate from the bone marrow to the peripheral blood, but there are very few of them- 1 in 10,000 cells. The source of obtaining these cells is the bone marrow and peripheral blood, which has recently become the main source of HSC for transplantation purposes.

Bone marrow stroma also contains stromal cells called mesenchymal stem cells (MSC). They are isolated from the bone marrow stroma. Their percentage is 0.01-0.0001% of bone marrow mononuclear cells. We can find them in adipose tissue, muscles, peripheral and umbilical blood, retina, liver, skin, pancreas and intestines. The best source of MSC is the bone marrow. They can be isolated from other sources such as the brain, eyes, skin, muscles, tooth pulp, blood vessels and the digestive system. Adipose tissue has become the primary source of these cells in animal regenerative medicine. Humans MSC are the best known, but these cells have also been found in mice, pigs, canine guinea pigs and rats.

Another type of stem cells are human dental pulp stem cells (DPSC) present in the central part of the pulp around the vessels and nerves. Their source may be naturally lost milk teeth. The pulp obtained in this way contains 12-20 stem cells from one incivise milk tooth. The most recent discoveries by scientists are amniotic fluid stem cells and neural stem cells (NSC). The first of these can be obtained during amniocentesis, chorionic villus sampling and postpartum placenta biopsy. Neural stem cells were found in the central nervous system in the granular layer of the cerebral cortex and in the dentate gyrus of the hippocampus. The latter discovery has high hopes for the treatment of neurological diseases.

IV. CELLULAR AGRICULTURE PROPERTIES

Stem cells present countless future prospects thanks to their diverse uses. A cell that has the ability to form any type of cell is referred to as totipotent. One of the possible use of stem cells is to produce cultured meat with them. The idea of producing specific parts of animals instead of breeding whole animals was presented by Winston Churchill in his essay "Fifty Years Hence". Winston Churchill's dream got a good chance of becoming a reality in 2013 when dr. Mark Post from Maastricht University created first cultured beef burger. Cultured meat is produced from stem cells that can be acquired through two main methods. The first method is to biopsy the animal's muscle tissue to isolate myosatellite stem cells from it. The second option is to take the stem cells from an animal embryo. Myosatellite cells are multipotent, which means they can only diversify into muscle cells in opposite of pluripotent stem cells from animal embryo. The obtained stem cells should be stimulated to divide and differentiate into myocytes in vitro. We can provide optimal conditions for stem cells within bioreactors. The development of artificial meat requires a specialized growth medium. Currently for cellular production of meat it requires a medium composed of high-quality water, amino acids, peptides, glucose, minerals and vitamins. Myocyte culture also requires the use of a few percent addition of fetal serum, which is necessary to stimulate division and differentiation of myocytes. We ensure a

tightly regulated environment for stem cell development within bioreactors. Development in the bioreactor can be divided into three phases. The First stage is the proliferation phase. Cells continue to proliferate only until the desired level of confluence is reached. The second step begins with the differentiation of cells into myocytes. At this phase cell culture requires electrical stimulation and mechanical. These actions are required to increase production of proteins, improve structure and prepare for building larger chains of proteins. If proper breeding conditions are ensured they form myotubes and then skeletal muscle tissue. The structure of the resulting meat products depends on time the duration of the cultivation and the conditions in the bioreactor. The synthetic meat created in the bioreactor has a 2d structure. At this stage, we are only able to generate layers of myocytes that are about one millimeter thick. It is also possible to make a 3d structure, but it would require special scaffolding or 3d printing technology. Despite the three-dimensional structure, the cultured meat obtained in this way cannot be compared to real meat. The scientific community claims that creation of structures that resemble real meat is theoretically possible, but would require vascular system to deliver nutrients to muscle tissue. The scientific community suggests that forming structures resembling real meat is theoretically achievable, but it would require a vascular system to supply nutrients to the muscle tissue. Stem cells are also used in cosmetology, with plant stem cells being the main type used in this field. They are retrieved from meristems, which are localized at strictly specified area. Most of the preparations and cosmetic products containing plant stem cells in fact contains stem cell extracts. The extracts and stem cells have different properties. Cosmetics containing these extracts have antioxidant, anti-aging and stimulating skin regeneration features. The initial step in extract production is choosing a plant with suitable characteristics, usually those that possess distinctive qualities and grow in harsh environments.. The cultivation of plant cells is much easier than that of animal cells. Next step is cut off a piece of the plant. The obtained plant must be cleaned to eliminate microorganisms. The purified material is cut into smaller pieces, which are placed on Petri dishes in a solid medium of a specific composition. Next step relies on selecting cell lines with the most desirable biochemical and metabolic features. After establishing cell culture in in vitro, industrial production can be started. Suspension cultures are moved into bioreactors, where the medium is enriched with macro- and microelements, vitamins, and growth regulators. Then the stem cell biomass is subjected to high pressure and enzymes. As a result of which extracts from stem cells are obtained. The use of cell culture techniques allows for extracts with elevated metabolite levels, unattainable by conventional means. Cosmetics formulated with plant stem cell extracts provide amazing regenerative, anti-inflammatory and moisturizing effects.

V. CELLULAR APPLICATION IN MEDICINE

Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) exhibit confirmed potential to differentiate into cartilaginous, osseous, and adipose tissues. Studies conducted in murine models demonstrated that, when introduced into a defect site, MSCs were capable of generating new cartilage tissue closely resembling the native, healthy cartilage. Moreover, clinical trials have been carried out in patients suffering from osteoarthritis, further supporting the therapeutic potential of MSC-based treatments. After applying the stem cells to the knee joint when surgeons were performing osteotomy. Around 42 further weeks they noticed the rebuild of articular cartilage that has been degenerated. Currently the stem cells are mostly used in orthopaedic surgeries that involve degenerative changes. Stem cells therapy is common among athletes, mostly because of it's cost and also they suffer from those injuries more commonly due to heavy overuse of joints, tendons and ligaments. The most common usage of stem cells in modern medicine is the transplantation of blood stem cells to cure blood and immune system diseases. Those stem cells can be found in the bone marrow and are taken from there for further transplantation. The stem cells are also used very often to create skin tissue for the transplant. The new skin is for the patients with significant burn damage. The transplanted skin however doesn't provide follicles, sweat and sebaceous gland, so it's not perfect and needs more additional research. Stem cells are also a hope for cardiac repair therapy. The idea is to use mesenchymal stem cells from umbilical cord and stem cells from bone marrow. It has been shown that these cells can form sarcomeric structures that are typical for heart. Point of this therapy is to cure effects of dead tissue after ischaemia of heart muscle. For the time being the problem is optimizing timing, dosage and delivery method.

Furthermore, there is a potential problem of influence of stem cell secretions. These cells also could be used to treat skeletal muscles injuries or degenerations. Common clinical trials involving use of stem cells are also present in neurology despite being very little evidence of those cell to convert into neural cells. The results of preclinical trials on animals are extremely positive, but clinical trials on humans are not showing that good results. The belief is that stem cells might be able to restore damage of neural cells coming from diseases like Alzheimer, or cerebral vascular accident. However, the treatment for Huntington disease using stem cells is very prominent. First the stem cells must be differentiated into GABAergic MSC after transplantation into the damaged brain are, next they have to survive and link axons correctly to globus pallidus and also receive impulses from cortex and substantia nigra. Stem cells can be used to heal wounds quicker. Mesenchymal stem cells can diversify into different cell types such as keratinocyte. They also appear to encourage factors that help the wound to heal quicker. Those factors are VEGF, IGF-1, EGF, growth factor of keratinocytes, angiopoietin and erythropoietin. The liver is an organ on which the stem cells therapy seems be one of the choices. The damage is mostly done in population via abusing alcohol, hepatitis B virus, or genetical disorders. Degenerated liver can be repaired using adult human liver cells, hematopoietic stem cells and mesenchymal stem cells. Adult human liver stem cells can express albumin and α -fetoprotein, they can also differentiate into functional hepatocytes. Hematopoietic and mesenchymal stem cells therapy can also be the option, they appear to contribute to liver regeneration however the mechanism is not totally understood.

VI. SUMMARY

There is no doubt that stem cell popularity is constantly growing. Promising results of experiments performed on animals show that there is still wide range of applications to discover. Owing to decades of prior research, our understanding of the fundamental principles governing stem cells has markedly improved. Although many aspects regarding their therapeutic potential remain unexplored, new concepts and hypotheses continue to emerge. Apart from the research done to better understand the physiology of stem cells, it has been equally important to determine their origins, to understand how they change over the human lifespan, and to assess whether such cells can be generated in vitro without relying on embryonic sources. That begs the question: What additional applications might stem cells enable? Current experimental evidence has demonstrated the feasibility of using plant-derived stem cells in cosmetology. Consequently, it is plausible that, in the future, cosmetic products incorporating plant stem cells could offer enhanced anti-aging or regenerative properties. Another promising direction involves the production of cultured meat from stem cells, thereby eliminating the need to slaughter animals and potentially bypassing the entire process of traditional livestock farming. At present, it is possible to generate several types of human tissues through stem cell-based technologies. Numerous therapeutic concepts for previously incurable diseases have emerged, offering hope to thousands of individuals worldwide. Even today, hematopoietic stem cells are routinely used to treat disorders of immune and hematologic systems, and skin can be engineered from stem cells for transplantation purposes. Consequently, it is conceivable that, in the future, similar approaches will enable the treatment of diseases affecting additional organ systems, including the nervous system.

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